

A Study of The Consumer Profile of Fresh Chicken B2B in Jakarta Province (Case study of Processed Noodle Restaurants)

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ABSTRACT: The study aims to comprehensively investigate the consumer profile of fresh chicken in Jakarta, with a special focus on processed noodle restaurants, especially ramen and bakmi restaurants as the main customers in business-to-business (B2B) transactions. This research is expected to serve as a basis for further analysis on how supply companies, especially the fresh chicken industry, can explore consumer preferences, purchasing behavior, motivational factors, and challenges faced in obtaining and using fresh chicken, especially in the DKI Jakarta province. The research was conducted using a survey method with a sampling technique using purposive purposive sampling with predetermined criteria of noodle processed restaurant managers. Farmers who were used as respondents amounted to 100 respondents. The analysis method used is descriptive with mode measurement or the most frequently occurring value. The results showed that the managers of processed noodle restaurants in Jakarta province are mostly in the age group of 26-35 years with 61% (61 people), 64% (64 people) have a Bachelor's degree. Most respondents have more than 3 years of work experience, namely 52% (52 people). The majority of the location distribution of processed noodle restaurants in DKI Jakarta province is in the city of South Jakarta (34%) and the majority of restaurants have an average number of workers between 10-20 people per outlet (83%), while 79% of restaurants have chicken meat needs between 10-20 kg.

KEYWORDS: Business to Business, Consumer, Fresh Chicken, Livestock Business, Processed Noodle Restaurant.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most popular culinary treasures in Indonesia, including province of Jakarta, is processed noodles such as bakmi and ramen. Noodles are also not only a culinary food choice, but can also be a staple food. This is possible because noodles as processed food from wheat or flour, can be processed easily, served practically, and meet the tastes of various groups of people based on income level, occupation, age, and gender (Rochmadika, et al., 2023). The World Instant Noodles Association (2023) explains that Indonesia's instant noodle consumption alone has reached 14.26 billion servings/packs. This number increased by 7.46% compared to the previous year (year-on-year/yoy) of 13.27 billion packs. Various menu options in the culinary sector with noodles as the main ingredient and chicken meat play an important component in creating quality culinary dishes as well as adding nutritional value. Chicken meat is an important component in every restaurant business, especially the processed noodle restaurant business, almost can be found in every menu choice in the restaurant there is a chicken component either as the main menu, alternative or complementary menu, this is because chicken meat is a favorite protein source that is highly preferred by Indonesians because it has a good taste and good texture, varied, easy to cook, and the price is more affordable than other types of meat (Onoh, et al., 2017). This favorability factor can be seen from the increasing amount of public consumption of chicken meat. According to the Agricultural Data and Information System Center (2022), the per capita consumption of broiler meat in Indonesia over the last ten years (2012-2022) has increased by 7.39% per year. The province with the highest average per capita consumption of broiler meat in Indonesia is the Special Capital Region (DKI) Jakarta, which is second only to Riau Islands Province. The average per capita consumption of broiler chicken meat in DKI Jakarta reached 10.198 kg per capita per year, which is much higher than the national average consumption of only 3.49 kg per capita per year.

The fresh chicken market plays a very important role in supporting the needs of the food industry, especially processed noodle restaurants, which not only rely on the quality of raw materials to maintain product reputation and excellence, but also must deeply understand their consumer profiles to develop effective marketing strategies. This study aims to comprehensively investigate the consumer profile of fresh chicken in Jakarta, with a special focus on processed noodle restaurants, especially ramen and noodle restaurants as the main customers in B2B business transactions. The points to be analyzed can be divided into 2 parts, namely the

profile of the restaurant manager who is responsible or related to the supplier and the profile of the restaurant. Through a case study approach by analyzing the profile of fresh chicken B2B consumers, especially processed noodle restaurants, this research can be a foundation for further analyzing how supply companies, especially the fresh chicken meat industry, can explore consumer preferences, purchasing behavior, motivational factors, and challenges faced in obtaining and using fresh chicken meat, especially in the DKI Jakarta province.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research was conducted in the province of Jakarta, which was purposively selected because it has the largest number of restaurants in Indonesia. There are five administrative cities in the province of the special capital region of Jakarta, namely the city of north jakarta and the thousand islands, the city of west jakarta, the city of south jakarta, the city of east jakarta, the city of central jakarta and the city of east jakarta which have been purposively selected. determining the number of respondents, namely the managers of processed noodle restaurants, used Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling. respondents were taken from each stratum based on the region. Then proportionally taken the amount so that the sample is obtained. Sampling was done in two stages. First, the respondents selected were derived from the total number of restaurant businesses in DKI Jakarta, namely 4,054 (BPS No. 31000-2239., 2021). The number of restaurant businesses will then be calculated using the Slovin formula so that the number of respondents to be taken can be determined. The second stage, dividing the number of respondents in each region in DKI Jakarta, which includes North Jakarta and Thousand Islands, West Jakarta, Central Jakarta, South Jakarta, and East Jakarta using the Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling formula so that 100 processed noodle restaurants are obtained as respondents and already represent each city. Sugiyono (2019) states that a questionnaire is a data collection tool that is done by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to answer. Respondents are asked to provide written answers to the questions asked. The questionnaire can be given directly to managers of processed noodle restaurants, namely ramen and noodle restaurants in the DKI Jakarta province to explore information about profiles including the age of the restaurant manager, gender, latest education, current job / position, length of work, income, and employee status, restaurant address, year of establishment, number of employees, ownership of business licenses, chicken meat requirements (kg / day). The sampling technique used in this study used purposive sampling technique as the selection of respondents. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2019). Therefore, the manager of the processed noodle restaurant was deliberately met by the researcher. The data analysis used is descriptive analysis. Descriptive analysis is an analysis that describes the data that has been processed so as to produce clear and easy-to-understand information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Age of respondent

This study aims to identify the diversity of characteristics of processed noodle restaurant managers based on age in the research location. The results showed that none of the restaurant managers were older than 56 years old. This may be due to several factors such as changes in work patterns and the older generation's preference for retirement. The data collected shows that the age group of 15-25 years old is only 5% (5 people). This can be explained by the fact that individuals in this age group may still be in the education stage or just starting their career, hence their relatively small number in restaurant management roles. In contrast, the 46-55 age group accounted for only 1% (1 person), which could be due to the tendency to reduce work activities and already being at the peak of their careers. The 36-45 age group recorded the second highest number of managers with 33 people (33%). This age group tends to be at the peak of their career, have sufficient experience, and financial stability that allows them to manage the restaurant business. Meanwhile, the 26-35 age group accounted for the largest number of managers with 61% (61 people). This age group is often in a productive phase of life, with high energy and ambition for career and business development. This dominance of productive age reflects the dynamics of the labor market and the potential growth of the restaurant industry, especially processed noodles. Meuti et al (2022), One of the factors that has an influence on employee productivity is the age factor. Age that is still in the productive period usually has a higher level of productivity compared to labor that is old so that the physical possession becomes weak and limited.

Table 1. Percentage of Respondent Age

No	Age	Number of People	Percentage (%)
1	15-25	5	5%
2	26-35	61	61%
3	36-45	33	33%
4	46-55	1	1%
Amount		100	100%

Respondent by education

This study aims to identify the diversity of characteristics of processed noodle restaurant managers based on the last level of education in the research location. The results showed that none of the respondents had the latest education at the elementary school, junior high school, or postgraduate/master level. The absence of respondents with elementary and junior high school education levels can be explained by job demands that require higher skills and knowledge, which are usually obtained through upper secondary or higher education. On the other hand, the absence of respondents with postgraduate/master education may be due to the tendency of individuals with such qualifications to opt for careers in more academic or professional fields that offer higher opportunities and compensation. The data collected shows that the group of managers with a senior high school education only accounted for 36% of the total respondents, i.e. 36 people. This small percentage indicates that while a high school education can provide an adequate knowledge base, for managerial positions in restaurants, higher education is often required to meet the more complex and dynamic demands of the job.

Table 2. Percentage of Respondent Education

No	Education	Number of People	Percentage (%)
1	Elementary school/ Junior high school	0	0%
2	Senior high school	36	36%
3	Bachelor Degree	64	64%
4	Master Degree	0	0%
Amount		100	100%

The largest dominance is in the group of managers with a bachelor's education, which reached 64% of the total respondents, namely 64 people. This suggests that a bachelor's degree is a common minimum qualification and is considered adequate for managerial roles in the processed noodle restaurant industry. Some factors that may contribute to this dominance include the comprehensive training in analytical, managerial and communication skills provided at the undergraduate education level. In addition, competition in the restaurant industry drives the need for more educated managers to ensure operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. The growing restaurant industry also offers attractive incentives for graduates, encouraging them to choose a career in this field. The results of this study reflect a trend in the restaurant industry that favors higher educational qualifications for managerial positions. Wiryawan and Rahmawati (2020), state that education level and career development have a significant impact on employee performance. Higher levels of education equip employees with broader knowledge and better skills, which in turn improve their ability to carry out tasks efficiently. Therefore, education directly affects employee performance.

Experience working in the same field

The majority of respondents, namely the managers of processed noodle restaurants in this study, have experience working in the same field, with the experience group of more than 3 years reaching the highest percentage, namely 52%. This shows that most participants have a high level of expertise and a deep understanding of the industry. Furthermore, the group with 1-2 years of work experience came in second with a percentage of 29%. This group is most likely made up of individuals who are relatively new but have started to accumulate relevant knowledge and skills.

Table 3. Percentage of Respondent Experience Working

No	Work Experience	Number of People	Percentage (%)
1	Less than 1 years (< 1 years)	17	17%
2	1-3 years	29	29%
3	More than 3 years	52	52%
Amount		100	100%

Finally, the group with less than 1 year of experience had the lowest percentage, at 17%. This low percentage reflects that few respondents are just starting out in this field, which may be due to factors such as minimum competency requirements for entry into the industry or employer preference for candidates with longer experience. This distribution of work experience provides a snapshot of the maturity and skill level of the workforce in the industry studied, as well as implications for operational dynamics and human resource development needs. Nurmega (2022), work experience is closely related to the ability and proficiency of employees in carrying out the assigned tasks. Work experience not only includes skills, expertise, and skills possessed, but also includes the length of time a person has worked in an agency. The more experience an employee has, the more capable he is in carrying out his work. The level of experience can be measured through the knowledge possessed and the skills mastered by employees. With adequate work experience, skill capabilities will increase, which in turn can improve employee performance.

Location distribution of processed noodle restaurants

Based on the results of data observation, it was found that the location of the majority of processed noodle restaurants is in South Jakarta. The characteristics of these restaurants can be understood through analyzing the distribution of the location of the restaurants involved in the study. The data shows that out of a total of 100 respondents taken, 34 restaurants are located in South Jakarta, making it the region with the highest number of restaurants. Furthermore, there are 20 restaurants in North Jakarta and Kepulauan Seribu, 17 restaurants in West Jakarta, 15 restaurants in Central Jakarta, and 14 restaurants in East Jakarta.

Table 4. Percentage of Respondent Location Distribution

No	Location by City	Number of Restaurants	Percentage (%)
1	North Jakarta and Kepulauan Seribu	20	20%
2	West Jakarta	17	17%
3	South Jakarta	34	34%
4	Central Jakarta	15	15%
5	East Jakarta	14	14%
Amount		100	100%

This distribution indicates that South Jakarta is the center of the highest concentration of noodle restaurants, which may be due to factors such as population density, consumption levels, and local culinary preferences. Understanding this geographical distribution is important for marketing strategies and restaurant business expansion, as well as providing insights into the market potential in each region of Jakarta. Hanum et al (2021), Suggests that business location selection has a significant influence on sales in the context of the restaurant business. A strategic location makes it easier for consumers to transact and increases business opportunities for greater profits. Therefore, entrepreneurs must carefully consider various important factors in choosing a business location to maximize profitability.

Total number of employees

Based on the results of data processing, it is found that the number of employees in processed noodle restaurants is generally above 10 employees. The characteristics of this restaurant can be understood through analyzing the number of employees working in processed noodle restaurants. The data shows that out of a total of 100 restaurants studied, 17 restaurants have more than 20 employees, while 83 restaurants have less than 20 employees. This finding indicates that the majority of processed noodle restaurants operate with smaller teams, which may be due to an efficient business model or a more limited operational scale. Meanwhile, restaurants with more than 20 employees tend to be larger entities with more complex operational needs.

Table 5. Percentage of Employee

No	Number of employees	Number of Restaurants	Percentage (%)
1	10 - 20 employees	83	83%
2	More than 20 employees	17	17%
Amount		100	100%

This headcount analysis provides important insights into the organizational structure and business scale of processed noodle restaurants, which can have implications for human resource management, productivity and the quality of service provided to customers. Kartika and Hepiana (2023), The number of employees has a significant influence on restaurant performance. Adequate staff numbers allow restaurants to provide fast and efficient service, which in turn increases customer satisfaction. This optimal service also allows for better personalization, which can enhance the customer experience and encourage their loyalty. In addition, sufficient headcount allows for effective task division, which can improve operational efficiency and reduce the risk of burnout among staff. With proper task distribution, every aspect of restaurant operations can run smoothly, from food preparation to customer service. Therefore, having enough employees is crucial to ensuring optimal restaurant performance and achieving sustainable business success.

Quantity of chicken meat needed per day

Based on the results of data processing, it was found that the majority of fresh chicken meat requirements per day from processed noodle restaurants ranged from 10-20 kg. The data shows that out of a total of 100 restaurants surveyed, 79% of restaurants have fresh chicken meat requirements in the range of 10-20 kg per day. Meanwhile, only 18% of restaurants require more than 21 kg of fresh chicken per day.

Table 6. Percentage of Quantity of Chicken Meat Needed

No	Chicken meat demand	Number of Restaurants	Percentage (%)
1	10 - 20 kg	79	79%
2	More than 20 kg	21	21%
Amount		100	100%

The high percentage in the 10-20 kg per day demand group indicates that most of the processed noodle restaurants operate on a medium scale, with a stable but not very large sales volume. This could be due to various factors such as seating capacity, customer visitation rate, and the size of the menu offered. On the other hand, the group of restaurants with fresh chicken meat requirements above 21 kg per day are likely to be restaurants with a larger scale of operation, perhaps with more branches or a more varied and popular menu among customers. This fresh chicken demand analysis provides an overview of the operational scale and market potential of each restaurant. This information is important for supply chain management, stock planning, and business strategy to efficiently meet customer demand.

CONCLUSION

The results showed that most of the managers of processed noodle restaurants in DKI Jakarta province are in the age group of 26-35 years, with a percentage of 61%. This shows that restaurant managers in this industry tend to be in the relatively young productive age range. In addition, the majority of processed noodle restaurants in DKI Jakarta province are located in the city of South Jakarta, which accounts for 33% of the total respondents. This location distribution indicates that South Jakarta is the center of business activity for processed noodle restaurants in the DKI Jakarta area. Most of the restaurants also have between 10-20 employees per outlet, which is 83%. This significant number of workers indicates the operational scale of processed noodle restaurants is quite large and requires effective human resource management. In addition, 79% of restaurants have a chicken meat requirement of between 10-20 kg per day, which illustrates the large demand for fresh chicken meat in the daily operations of processed noodle restaurants. These findings provide important insights for fresh chicken supply companies in developing more effective marketing strategies. By understanding the demographic profile of restaurant managers, the geographical location of

restaurants, the scale of the workforce, and the demand for raw materials, companies can develop more targeted marketing strategies. This knowledge allows the company to customize their products and services according to the specific needs of processed noodle restaurants in DKI Jakarta, improving customer satisfaction and competitiveness in the market. In addition, an in-depth understanding of operational needs and consumer preferences can assist supplying companies in planning more efficient supplies and reducing the risk of overstocking or under-stocking.

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